

ELIMINATION OF NOISY OPERATION OF DAMAS REAR SUSPENSIONS.

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Modern cars use engines that are relatively small in size and mass, and generate high power due to their high speed. However, the torque generated on the shafts of these engines (if this torque is transmitted directly to the driving wheels of the car without changing it) is not enough to drive the car in different road conditions. To drive the car, increasing the torque on its leading wheels is partly done with the help of a gearbox. But the car moves in the right gear with a relatively high speed during operation. So, in the correct transmission, the torque on the engine shaft would be transmitted to the leading wheels without changing, that is, not enough to drive the car [1].

The driving bridge usually combines the following mechanisms into one unit: main gear, differential and half-axes. The indicated mechanisms are structurally located in the common crankcase of the driving bridge and serve to transmit the torque to the wheels. Bridge mechanisms increase the transmitted torque and distribute it to the wheels depending on the conditions of contact of each wheel with the road.

Previous bridge base (Fig. 1) two at the tip up coming bent bump has been compound The beam is Don't be surprised medium part down towards bent and the engine from frame down placing enable gives of the bridge top on the surface suspension resource fasten for support There are 3 pitches . Beam to the bump Broken 4 is placed and biker fixed , it is rotatable saffani installation for service does sapfa axis in bearings the wheel doll is fixed , sapfanning himself while turner using lever 5 in the brokenda turn takes. Previous wheels independent to the suspension have has been back should be conducted In cars previous bridge short beam in the form of is a car is attached to the body. He is one of the moment in itself the engine fasten service for car. [2,3,4,5].

Figure 1. Leading didn't happen previous bridge the beam

Car suspensions the work in the process Leader to the wheel from the transmission given screw driver of torque pusher Rt power referrer part through the body. forward push , elastic part the way from irregularities being transmitted impulses softens and extinguisher part elastic part at the expense of vertical in the direction moving the vibration of the body extinguishes [6,7,8,9,10] .

Car suspensions referrer part not only transversely , longitudinally , laterally effect doing forces transmits , maybe of the wheel to the body, relatively also determines the action . Referral part of type looking suspensions independent and independent types breaks down (Fig. 2).

a) independent suspension _ b) independent suspension

2 . Car suspensions .

Independent on suspensions left or right wheels each other with not connected is , left (or right) to the wheel the way from unevenness effect reached impulse to the right (or left) wheel not transmitted . To this modern front suspensions of cars MATIZ, SPARK, TIKO , NEXIA example be takes Independent in suspensions and left and right wheels one one with connected is , left (or right) to the wheel the way from the unevenness effect reached impulses to the right (or left) wheel

is transmitted . Light MATIZ, TIKO , DAMAS, NEKSYA cars back suspensions , luggage car and of buses previous and back suspensions example be takes _

of wheels to the road relatively movement his kinematics determines _ Suspension kinematics him the body. of the car longitudinally axis relatively vibration provides and of the vehicle walking fluency , manageability , stability such as exploitative features active effect is enough [13,14,15].

The disadvantages of Damaz car transmission are that due to the large spiral angle of the wheel teeth, the tooth surfaces slide against each other. In addition, it is relatively difficult to prepare the gears of this transmission, the degree of accuracy in their assembly is high, because the effect of a small inaccuracy is quickly felt.

However, these disadvantages do not affect the advantages of the hypoid transmission. Worm main drives differ from gear drives in their compactness and noiseless operation. But this transmission is small compared to conical and hypoid transmissions, and because of the use of expensive metal (bronze) in its manufacture, it is hardly used in cars [11,12,16]. Modern cars use engines that are relatively small in size and mass, and generate high power due to their high speed. However, the torque generated on the shafts of these engines (if this torque is transmitted directly to the driving wheels of the car without changing it) is not enough to drive the car in different road conditions. To drive the car, increasing the torque on its leading wheels is partly done with the help of a gearbox. But the car moves in the right gear with a relatively high speed during operation. So, in the correct transmission, the torque on the engine shaft would be transmitted to the leading wheels without changing, that is, not enough to drive the car.

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